

**Financial translation, a neglected field:
The case of the Key Investor Information document**

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Abstract

By looking at the Key Investor Information document (KIID), the present article shows how the area of finance is still considerably unexplored in Translation Studies, despite the increased interest that economic and financial texts have attracted among translation scholars in the last decade. The article describes the KIID and its background and then focuses on its relevance to Translation Studies, as well as to translation practice and, more generally, to society. Never before examined within Translation Studies, the KIID is a mandatory regulatory document aimed at retail investors, and its underlying financial product increases financing opportunities for companies, especially when crossing international borders, where the document's translation into the target country's language is compulsory. The KIID has very specific characteristics that make it a financial genre in its own right, due to grow in importance because of several factors. In the article, its main characteristics are presented and discussed from a Translation Studies perspective, on the basis of both the regulations that gave rise to it and a parallel and comparable corpus study.

Key-words: translation, economics, finance, legal requirements, Key Investor Information document.

1. Introduction

Some ten years ago, very little had been written about financial translation, or even economic translation in general (commercial translation is another matter altogether). Partly thanks to the interest sparked in them by the major economic crisis that we have been suffering, the situation has recently improved. However, almost everything remains to be done. One could say that Translation Studies lives with its back turned to a field, that of economic (and financial) translation, whose weight in the professional translation industry is remarkable—as far as I can see as a translator working in the field since 2001—and whose impact on our lives is significant—this is illustrated by the fact that, outside of the English-speaking world, the statements made by institutions such as the European Central Bank and the International Monetary Fund are received in translation.

The described picture is all the more striking when one takes into consideration the vast body of studies by economists on the external communication of major economic institutions (not only supranational ones, but also national ones like the United States Federal Reserve and the Bank of Japan). These studies deal with, among other aspects, their lexica, the

clarity and effect of their messages and the development of their communication policies over time (Bernal and Gnabo 2009; Jansen and de Haan 2010; Rosa 2011; Lamla and Lein 2011; Bulíř et al. 2012; and Büchel 2013).

Despite the fact that their statements, except in English-speaking countries, are usually received in translation (it should be reminded that the working language of the supranational institutions is English), virtually nothing has been said about these statements' translation.

In this paper, I look at a financial genre of great social import that has impacted the translation industry significantly and is yet to be explored within Translation Studies. I am referring to the Key Investor Information document (commonly known as either 'KII' or 'KIID', and hereinafter referred to as the latter). This document is required by the European Union since several years ago as an investor protection method.

In the next section, I summarize the KIID's background. Section 3 is dedicated to describing the KIID, while in Sections 4 and 5, its relation to translation and a series of general considerations about its translation are set out, respectively. Multiple examples from actual English and Spanish KIIDs (in translation as well as originals) are provided in Section 6, a small, complementary corpus study that is followed by my conclusions. Specific

references to the Spanish situation are made throughout the paper. The situation in other EU Member States can be expected to be (only) slightly different.

2. The Key Investor Information document's background

In 1985, the EU Council Directive 85/611/EEC took a further step towards the creation of a single European market in financial services by coordinating provisions relating to "undertakings for collective investment in transferable securities (UCITS)" (or investment funds that were suitable for retail investors). The degree of harmonization achieved by this Directive soon proved insufficient for the intended purpose of enabling funds that had been authorised in one Member State to be sold in other Member States without further authorisation. This gave rise in the early 1990s to a proposal for a new directive. Known as 'UCITS II', the proposed new Directive was not passed because of its complexity. One decade later, amendments to the first Directive succeeded in being adopted. They formed the Directives 2001/107/EC and 2001/108/EC, known as 'UCITS III'. These amendments contained the germ of the KIID, i.e. the 'simplified prospectus'. In addition to the 'prospectus' (a legal document describing the investment product in detail) and to the annual and half-yearly reports (in short, the accounts), a simplified prospectus had to be published for each fund (or investment company). The aim of this document was to protect the investor by providing him/her with the following information, before the investment

was made: a summary of the fund's objectives and investment policy, the risks associated with investing in it, its past performance, and the charges involved in the investment, as well as commercial information (how to buy or sell units (or shares), whether dividend income would be distributed or reinvested, etc.) and the indication of the type of investor that the product was designed for. The simplified prospectus had to be kept up-to-date and would be valid in all Member States, although conditions differed; for example, in Spain, as opposed to other states, a sworn translation into the country's official language was required.

For several reasons, the aim of the simplified prospectus was not achieved. The document contained legal and technical language that was difficult to comprehend for the retail investor; in the case of certain products, the content requirements resulted in a lengthy text that discouraged reading; comparison between different funds, which the simplified prospectus was intended to facilitate, was hindered by the specific content requirements imposed by the different Member States; lastly, the costs that the document involved were excessive.

In 2009, a new directive, 2009/65/EC or 'UCITS IV', superseded the Directives 2001/107/EC and 2001/108/EC and, among other changes, replaced the simplified prospectus with the KIID in order to tackle these problems.

3. What the Key Investor Information document is

The Directive 2009/65/EC establishes the outline of the KIID. This must be written in non-technical language and in a concise manner, and must be presented in an EU-wide common format which facilitates comparison of products. As far as its content is concerned, it must include the essential characteristics of the product: objectives and investment policy, past performance (or performance scenarios), costs, and risk/reward profile (the latter accompanied by any information that may be necessary for the potential investor to gain a clear idea of the risks associated with the investment).

UCITS IV's implementing legislation, the European Commission Regulation 583/2010, of 1 July 2010, indicates in detail the KIID's format of presentation and content, to the extent that it even determines the sections that the document must include, the order in which they must appear, their titles and their required content. The choice of a regulation for implementing the Directive should be highlighted. Given that regulations are directly applicable in all Member States, this choice guaranteed that the requirements would be identical across the EU and ensured the harmonization of both form and content, with a view to making the products offered by the different management companies or investment companies comparable.

The KIID's maximum length is two pages of A4-sized paper with a readable font size (except in the case of structured funds, where three pages apply). With respect to the language to be employed, the document must facilitate comprehension by a retail investor. To this end, the Regulation urges to write in a clear and concise manner and to avoid both technical terms (when words in common usage can be employed) and jargon. It is worth mentioning in this regard that the Spanish law that incorporates the new provisions relating to UCITS—the 'Ley 35/2003 de Instituciones de Inversión Colectiva', or Law 35/2003 on Collective Investment Undertakings—makes clear reference to the general public as the intended recipient.

The content itself must focus on relevant information, on "the key information that investors need" (Commission Regulation 2010, Article 5(1)(c)). This must be fair and not misleading. The document should suffice for the investor to be able to make an informed investment decision.

It should be highlighted that the Regulation even specifies the phrasing of certain information. For example, under the document title, the following statement must appear:

This document provides you with key investor information about this fund. It is not marketing material. The

information is required by law to help you understand the nature and the risks of investing in this fund. You are advised to read it so you can make an informed decision about whether to invest. (Commission Regulation 2010, Article 4(3))

In Spanish, the mandatory phrasing is:

El presente documento recoge los datos fundamentales sobre este fondo que el inversor debe conocer. No se trata de material de promoción comercial. La ley exige que se facilite esta información para ayudarle a comprender la naturaleza del fondo y los riesgos que comporta invertir en él. Es aconsejable que lea el documento para poder tomar una decisión fundada sobre la conveniencia o no de invertir en él. (Reglamento de la Comisión 2010, artículo 4(3))

Likewise, the information concerning the product's authorisation must be phrased as follows: "This fund is authorised in [name of Member State] and regulated by [identity of competent authority]" (Commission Regulation 2010, Article 4(12)) / "Este fondo está autorizado en [nombre del Estado miembro] y está regulado por [identidad de la autoridad competente]"

(Reglamento de la Comisión 2010, artículo 4(12)). And the date of publication must appear in the following sentence, relating to the accuracy of the supplied information: "This key investor information is accurate as at [the date of publication]" (Commission Regulation 2010, Article 4(13)) / "Los presentes datos fundamentales para el inversor son exactos a [fecha de publicación]" (Reglamento de la Comisión 2010, artículo 4(13)).

With regard to this latter sentence, it should be mentioned that, like the simplified prospectus, the KIID must be kept up-to-date. Therefore, it should be reviewed in the following circumstances: when the information on which it is based changes significantly; when the prospectus, the fund rules or, in the case of investment companies, the company's instrument of incorporation are going to be modified; annually, at least (Commission Regulation 2010, Article 22).

There are specific cases of UCITS for which the general conditions of form and content must be adapted; for example, the already mentioned case of structured funds, or the following ones: funds with different compartments, with different share classes, belonging to a master-feeder structure, and lastly, funds of funds. The Regulation offers guidelines for these specific cases.

Although the Regulation also provides very specific details on how to present the risk-reward profile (through a graphic indicator), the charges, and the past performance, the KIID's definition does not end in the Regulation; instead, it is completed by both a KIID template created by the Committee of European Securities Regulators (CESR) and some guidelines issued by the national authorities (in the Spanish case, especially the Comisión Nacional del Mercado de Valores, or CNMV (Spanish National Securities Market Commission)). In addition, the CESR has published a guide containing style and formatting recommendations, *CESR's guide to clear language and layout for the Key Investor Information document* (2010b). The CESR's template and guide are in English, with no institutional translations into other languages available.

The template shows the content and layout of the KIID for a standard UCITS, and, as indicated in its accompanying information, must be used as a model when preparing KIIDs (CESR 2010a, 3). Figures 1 and 2 are a reproduction of its two pages. Note the five sections that the template is divided into; these correspond to the five types of information that, according to the Directive, the KIID must include. Note also how the risk-reward profile, the charges and the performance (second, third and fourth section, respectively) are represented. Finally, observe the reference to the home state of the fund in the fourth bullet point of the last section: "A statement that tax legislation of the fund's Home State may have an impact

on the personal tax position of the investor".¹ This reference brings me to the next section of my article, where I will focus on the KIID's relation to translation.

INSERT FIG 1 HERE

Figure 1: Template for the KIID, page 1 (CESR 2010a, 4).

INSERT FIG 2 HERE

Figure 2: Template for the KIID, page 2 (CESR 2010a, 5).

4. The Key Investor Information document and translation

The Directive 2009/65/EC establishes as "obligatory investor disclosures" the KIID, the prospectus and the annual and half-yearly reports. It stipulates that, of all of these documents, only the former one must be translated if the fund is to be marketed in a Member State other than the state where it was authorised:

To facilitate access of UCITS to the markets of other Member States, the UCITS should be required to translate only the key investor information into the official language or one of the official languages of a UCITS host

Member State or a language approved by its competent authorities. Key investor information should specify the language(s) in which other obligatory disclosure documents and additional information are available.
(Directive 2009, Recital 66)

The Spanish Law 35/2003 on Collective Investment Undertakings, in its consolidated version (that is, following the transposal of the Directive 2009/65/EC), specifies that, in Spain, the KIID must be presented in Spanish or in a language that has been approved by the CNMV. So far, the CNMV has not extended the allowed languages beyond Spanish.

With respect to whether the translation must be sworn or not, unlike for the simplified prospectus, a simple translation is allowed ("Translations should be produced under the responsibility of the UCITS, which should decide whether a simple or a sworn translation is necessary"; Directive 2009, Recital 66). However, the Directive provides that civil liability can be incurred for a translation that is misleading, inaccurate or inconsistent with the prospectus. The same applies to a KIID in its original language. In fact, civil liability can only be incurred in relation to KIIDs for content that is misleading, inaccurate or inconsistent with the prospectus.

As far as the other documents composing the "obligatory investor disclosures" are concerned, the Directive (2009, Article 94(1)(c)) indicates that they must be available either in an official language of the host Member State, or in a language approved by the competent authorities of this state, or *in a language "customary in the sphere of international finance"* (my italics). As pointed out by the specialist in commercial law Josefina García Pedroviejo (2011: 88), the latter means English. Spanish legislation (the consolidated Law 35/2003) seems to place more emphasis on the fact that the lingua franca of finance will be accepted: "The prospectus and the annual and half-yearly reports, as well as their modifications, shall be presented in Spanish, or in a language customary in the sphere of international finance, or in a language approved by the CNMV" (Ley 35/2003 2014, artículos 15 and 16; my translation).

UCITS IV came into force on 1 July 2011; however, the UCITS were allowed twelve months as from that date to substitute KIIDs for simplified prospectuses. That UCITS IV has impacted the translation industry, as I anticipated in my introduction, is logical. Its significance in the investment industry and, more generally, in society is also evident. In relation to these latter spheres, it is worth mentioning that the Spanish Law 35/2003 on Collective Investment Undertakings, since it was first drawn up, starts by stating, in its explanatory memorandum, that "collective investment is the natural channel for the participation of Spanish households in the capital

markets", and underlines "its dual nature as both a disintermediated financing formula [in other words, a financing formula that does not require the intermediation of credit institutions] and also a privileged savings vehicle for retail investors" (Ley 35/2003 2003, 39220; my translation).

Returning to the translation industry, KIIDs have become one of the most recurring genres for financial translators, which is not surprising given the increasing volume of (cross-border) UCITS funds (KPMG 2012, 4; Lipper European Fund Market Review 2013, quoted in European Commission 2015; EFAMA 2015). My own experience with them, in case it might be of interest, began in June 2011, one month before the UCITS IV Directive came into force, and as far as I have been able to observe, the demand has not ceased since then. It does not seem likely that it will diminish, given that the European Union plans to extend the requirement of a KIID to other types of investment products (termed by the EU as ‘Packaged Retail Investment Products’, or ‘PRIPs’), whose overall value in the European market at the beginning of 2014 was 10 trillion euros (compared to the 6 trillion euros in UCITS funds)² (European Commission 2014a and 2014b).

It is, therefore, worth analysing KIIDs from a Translation Studies point of view.

5. The translation of the Key Investor Information document: general considerations

When I arrived in academia some ten years ago, I was surprised to find that economic (and financial) translation was considered by many as purely technical, as a question of terminology, while in my experience the reality could be very different. As I showed in Serón-Ordóñez (2005), phenomena that are frequently associated with literary language, such as metaphors, often populate economic language; these, however, had barely been explored within Translation Studies.

At the present time, in a sense, we seem to have gone from one extreme to the other, i.e. to focusing on economic metaphors and neglecting other equally important aspects. Hence there abound the studies about metaphor in economics (such as Tcaciuc 2012, Nicolae 2013, Mirzoyeva 2014 and Zheng 2015), as well as those about neologisms, which were already abundant in the past (e.g. Ferard 2009). As Gallego-Hernández (2012, 83-102) has reminded us, abbreviations are usually associated with economic translation as well.

Interestingly, the KIID rejects all of these phenomena, for the sake of clarity. KIIDs seem to have fallen out of the radar of Translation Studies. In fact, they do not appear in recent categorizations of economic texts (Alcalde 2014, Tolosa-Igualada 2014). It could be argued that they are comprised in categories such as the usual one of ‘Prospectus’ or that of ‘Product description’ (Tolosa-Igualada 2014, 36), but the KIID is precisely intended

to differentiate itself from the prospectus, as mentioned above, refusing its legal and technical language, and does not constitute a simple product description either, as this type of descriptions can reasonably be expected to be of a commercial nature and the KIID must exclude any "commercial-speak", which should go into separate marketing documents (remember the statement "This document provides you with key investor information about this fund. It is not marketing material").

Despite their having been overlooked by translation scholars, KIIDs have characteristics that make them worth reflecting upon. The translator facing a KIID should not only be knowledgeable in the subarea of investment funds. He/she should additionally have studied the applicable UCITS regulations, in order to be able to comply with the legal requirements concerned, which also apply to the translated versions, as pointed out in the previous section.

The translation cannot exceed the two or three pages established, with a font size not smaller than Sans Serif 10 or equivalent (unless narrow columns are used, in which case the font can be a little smaller) (CESR 2010b, 8). This should be taken into account by the client when writing the original, given the normally higher space requirements of certain languages, such as Spanish and German, relative to others like English.

The translation should also respect the phrasing required in the target language for certain statements and for the section titles, and avoid, among other linguistic phenomena, technical terms, jargon, synonymy, homonymy and polysemy, foreign terms, and acronyms and other abbreviations (for example, 'NAV' and 'b.p.'). Consequently, it is not surprising that translators including myself have received instructions to stray from the source text when a more literal translation is unclear, or when the client may have overlooked any of the legal requirements. Facilitating comprehension and ensuring legal compliance take the priority.

The importance of these new instructions for Translation Studies at a time in which the discipline strives to empower translators by dispelling their false perception as robotic casual workers is incontestable.³ Even more so if one takes into account the translator's privileged position with respect to the "subject-matter expert" as far as the primary goal of guaranteeing comprehensibility is concerned.⁴ Not having such a close or tight relationship with the area of finance, the translator will be more able to identify (and avoid) technical terms and jargon. The subject-matter expert, highly accustomed to this language, can have trouble identifying what would not be commonly understood. As a matter of fact, Warren Buffet, in his preface to the US Securities and Exchange Commission volume *A plain English handbook: How to create clear SEC disclosure documents* (1998), recommends experts in accounting/finance to write with a non-expert in

mind, mentioning that he writes Berkshire Hathaway's annual report as if he was talking to his sisters:

Though highly intelligent, they are not experts in accounting or finance. They will understand plain English, but jargon may puzzle them. My goal is simply to give them the information I would wish them to supply me if our positions were reversed. (Buffet 1998, 2)

Moreover, the translator's experience translating is, as far as I have been able to observe, a key asset in avoiding the use of synonyms throughout a given text,⁵ and his/her linguistic awareness is of great value in avoiding other sources of ambiguity or obscurity, such as homonymy, polysemy and certain constructions. This does not mean that translators have everything on their side: they might have to make an extra effort to avoid terminology and constructions that do not comply with the European regulations and that they may systematically use in (when rendering) other financial genres.

The task at hand may seem easy, but a look at actual KIIDs reveals that it is not; it requires meticulous work, besides the already mentioned knowledge of both the subarea of investment funds and the UCITS regulations. In the next section, I will provide a series of examples that illustrate all the above and reflect other relevant aspects.

6. The translation of the Key Investor Information document: a small corpus study

The examples below have been extracted from a small corpus of 30 KIIDs in English and Spanish, issued by different companies. The corpus contains 10 original English KIIDs and their Spanish translations, as well as 4 translated English KIIDs with different source languages (French from France and from Switzerland, German and Finnish) and 6 original Spanish KIIDs. The documents were selected randomly through an Internet search.

For convenience, the examples have been inserted into a brief, recapitulatory description of the KIID. They first reflect issues in the macrostructure of the documents, later in their microstructure.

As shown in the template for the KIID (see Figure 1), this is to be headed by the title "Key Investor Information" and a statement defining the document. The first aspect in the corpus that is worth noting is the modification of this meta-information in three out of the four translated English KIIDs, especially in two of them, where the statement is not standardized. Furthermore, in one of these latter cases, the document is defined as commercial information ("Considered a commercial document, the [present] English translation..."), contrary to the standardized statement; according to the document, only the original French version is binding (ex. 1). In the

other case where the statement has been modified, its content is untouched, since the English translation simply follows closely the also French source text. In this same KIID, the title does not adhere to the official text either, having information added to it (both the term 'Document' and the unit class) (2). In the third and last KIID with modifications in the meta-information, the title also shows the addition of the term 'Document'; more importantly, a paragraph has been added to the Practical Information section indicating that the document is a translation and that the original Finnish KIID will prevail in case of discrepancies between these two versions (3). Similarly, in the remaining translated English KIID, the paragraph on the civil liability for information that is misleading, inaccurate or inconsistent with the prospectus specifies that this liability is only applicable to the original German version, and a fairly large notice at the bottom of each page indicates that the English translation is provided only for convenience (4).

What these KIIDs show is that, sometimes, the KIID is being translated into English not with the intention of complying with legal requirements but just for information purposes, probably with the ultimate aim of distributing the fund concerned to a wider audience in the fund's home state, including investors who do not speak the original language of the document. This "documentary" instead of "instrumental" form of translation (following Nord 1988/2005) increases opportunities for translators into English.

The KIID's identification is followed by the identification of both the fund and the management company. Regarding this heading, which is highly similar in all the documents in the corpus, it is worth mentioning that Spanish investors may miss certain data due to their having been left in English. This occurs particularly with respect to the share class. When it appears in a fully developed form rather than abbreviated, like in "Euro Class A-Hedged - Distribution shares" (5), it is usually translated, but at times, it is not, potentially depriving the investor of useful information such as (following ex. 5) the fact that the share class uses a hedging strategy to minimise risk (this is implied by the term 'Hedged', which can be translated as *con cobertura*), or the fact that any income arising from the fund will be distributed rather than reinvested ("Distribution shares", *acciones de reparto*). When the share class details appear abbreviated, like in "EUR Acc" (6), they usually remain in English, with the same effect. In these cases, the investor without the corresponding English skills will only be able to obtain the missing data when they reappear, translated, further down in the document.

In the section titles, remarkable discrepancies have been observed. While the original documents follow the CESR's template strictly, the translated versions deviate from it more often than one would expect. In translated Spanish, the section "Objectives and Investment Policy" sometimes turns into *Política de inversión y objetivos* (7) (Investment Policy and Objectives;

note the reverse order), even though the section content shows first the objectives and then the policy. In both translated Spanish and translated English, the last two sections sometimes show titles different from the standardized ones, more specifically *Rentabilidad pasada* (8) (Past Performance) as opposed to *Rentabilidad histórica* (Historical Performance), "Historical Performance" (9) as opposed to "Past Performance", *Información útil* (10) (Useful Information) as opposed to *Información práctica* (Practical Information), and "Useful Information" (11) as opposed to "Practical Information". As will have been observed, the content itself does not vary, but the Commission Regulation is very clear in providing the section titles.

The content of the different sections is characterized syntactically by sentences with a simple structure (there abound the subject-verb-complement constructions, and subordinate clauses are scarce). In addition, sentences tend to be short. Some examples follow, showing that the mentioned features are shared by the English and Spanish originals, as well as by the Spanish translations:

—"The success of the Fund will depend primarily upon the accuracy of the Investment Manager's views of the relative merits of companies. The Investment Manager has a high level of choice as to how to make investments for the Fund." (12-13), translated in the corpus as *El éxito del*

Fondo dependerá principalmente de la precisión de la visión que tenga el Gestor de Inversiones sobre los méritos relativos de las empresas. El Gestor de Inversiones goza de gran libertad de elección en cuanto al modo de realizar las inversiones del Fondo. (14-15);

—"Past performance is not a guide to future performance." (16), translated in the corpus as *La rentabilidad histórica no garantiza la rentabilidad futura.* (17);⁶

—"The depositary is [bank name] plc." (18), translated in the corpus as *El depositario es [bank name] Plc.* (19);

—*El fondo invierte más del 60% de su exposición total en activos de renta variable.* (20) (The Fund invests more than 60% of its overall exposure in equity assets.);

—*La inversión en activos de entidades portuguesas es inferior al 25% de la exposición total.* (21) (Investment in assets of Portuguese organizations is lower than 25% of the overall exposure.);

—*El fondo no está expuesto a riesgo divisa.* (22) (The Fund is not exposed to currency risk.)

Also with respect to syntax, the active voice largely predominates: "The Investment Manager will use a wide range of derivative instruments" (23), "You can buy and sell shares in the Fund on any working day in Luxembourg" (24). Note, additionally, the markedly personal and direct tone used, which was set by the regulators in the opening statement; for

example, investors are usually referred to as ‘you’, versus more general forms such as ‘investors’, which are common in other financial genres, as is the passive voice (the latter especially in English—“Shares in the Fund can be bought and sold on any working day in Luxembourg.” would be a standard sentence).

At the lexical semantic level, things complicate, for two main reasons: first, the difficulty in keeping to the standardized lexicon; second, the difficulty in determining what needs to be clarified or explained. The former leads to widespread inconsistencies and, thus, cases of synonymy, subtracting clarity. For example, there often co-exist in the same KIID *gastos* and *comisiones* for ‘charges’ (25), the former translation being the one used in the regulations, where the latter translation is reserved for ‘fees’. Similarly, *valor (de referencia)* and *índice (de referencia)* appear interchangeably in multiple KIIDs for ‘benchmark’ (26). This English term has been translated as *valor de referencia* in the regulations. While *índice de referencia* is a more common translation, it is not suited to all contexts due to its being more specific, which is probably the reason why it was not used in the regulations. Its use in the KIIDs leads to the above mentioned synonymy problems, if not to more potentially problematic issues of homonymy/polysemy: when *de referencia* is omitted in *valor de referencia*, it could perhaps be mistaken for the Fund’s value (*valor (del Fondo)*) or for other concepts that in Spanish bear the term *valor*, such as security

(meaning financial instrument), a concept that is often alluded to in the KIIDs to refer to a share and that is termed precisely *valor* in Spanish. Context helps to clarify meaning, but a cursory reading and lack of familiarity with the subject may cause comprehension problems.

Discrepancies between different KIIDs have been detected in the translation for ‘net asset value’, a term that is rendered as *valor de inventario neto* in the regulations but which is commonly translated as—among other translations—*valor liquidativo*. This latter translation often slips into the KIIDs (27), hindering comparability.

Similarly, ‘transaction costs’ is rendered in the different KIIDs as either *costes de transacción* (like in the regulations) or *costes de (las) operaciones* (28); and ‘running costs’ appears as either *costes de funcionamiento* (the standardized translation) or *costes de gestión* (29). Although the context where all of these terms appear helps to notice that the realities alluded to are the same, again, the discrepancies do not facilitate the KIIDs’ intended comparability.

As regards the difficulty in determining what needs to be clarified or explained, it should be stressed that one of the most salient features of the KIID is its tendency to clarify or explain, which is in line with the comprehensibility requirement. The abundant clarifications or explanations

can appear in brief parenthetical remarks, as well as occupy whole paragraphs. There follow some examples:

—"The risk and reward is calculated on the basis of the share price volatility (*the ups and downs of its value*) over the prior 5 years" (30);

—"A key feature of the Fund is that it invests in company shares whilst at the same time seeking to hedge (*or minimise*) the market related risks of doing so" (31);

—"At least 50% of the investment will be in fixed income securities [*investments which provide a certain level of income or interest*] which are issued by companies" (32);

—"To this end, the Subfund primarily invests in ordinary shares (*shares that grant the shareholder voting rights at the general meeting of the Company*)" (33);

—"Esta participación es de acumulación, *es decir, los rendimientos obtenidos son reinvertidos*" (34) (This is an accumulation unit, *that is, any income earned is reinvested*);

—"Credit risk: The Fund is exposed to *the risk that the credit quality of any direct or indirect debtor of the Fund (be it a state, a financial institution or a corporate) deteriorates or that any such entity defaults. This could cause the net asset value of the Fund to decline*" (35);

—"Riesgo de crédito: *Es el riesgo de que el emisor de los activos de renta fija no pueda hacer frente al pago del principal y del interés*" (36) (Credit

risk: It is *the risk that the issuer of the fixed income assets cannot make the principal and interest payments*).

While there seems to be consensus that certain concepts, such as credit risk and accumulation unit/share, require explanation (see exs. 34-36; cf. ex. 6), other concepts, by being sometimes clarified, sometimes not, seem to reveal uncertainty, hesitation, or lack of agreement. This is the case of currency risk (37) and counterparty risk (38). Hence risk factors are not always explained, despite the regulatory requirement to identify and explain the risks (without over-burdening the KIID with technicalities).

Another interesting case is that of derivatives (39). More often than not, this concept is left unexplained, even though derivatives are complex financial instruments and, in the same KIIDs where the concept is not explained, more straightforward concepts such as volatility and liquidity (meaning the ability to be sold) are clarified.

As mentioned above, translators among whom I am included have received instructions to stray from the source text when our translation is unclear or when the client may have overlooked any of the legal requirements. The absence of explanations such as these could be an opportunity for the translator to step in and contribute to the authoring of KIIDs. Judging from

my experience, the translator's possible help would be appreciated by the client, thus contributing to raising the translators' status.

Continuing with the same reflection, the corpus shows other potential areas for the translator's intervention, ranging from the lack of precise references to the Prospectus (whose inclusion had been mandated by the CESR's template), to the presence of seemingly biased information (impartiality being a regulatory requirement, as mentioned in Section 3), to specific statements that are missing (such as the required indication that the entry charge shown is the maximum that might be subtracted from the investor's money before the investment is made).

Also in relation to the translator's role and status, two errors found in the translated Spanish KIIDs are worth pointing out. They both affect meaning. This is especially the case of a common mistranslation whereby the fund's potential risk and reward turn into *el riesgo potencial y la rentabilidad del fondo* (the potential risk and the reward of the Fund). Although the English adjective 'potential' could just modify 'risk' (as interpreted in the translation), it actually modifies both 'risk' and 'reward'. This is made clear by the context, where it is stated that the greater the potential reward, the greater the risk.

The other error I would like to point out is the lack of a comma between "y" and "teniendo" in "el fondo invertirá en activos líquidos y en otras inversiones afines [...] y teniendo en cuenta el objetivo del Fondo, ocasionalmente dichas inversiones podrán ser considerables". The comma concerned is present in the source text: "the fund will invest in cash and other cash-like investments [...] and, bearing in mind the objective of the Fund, from time to time such investment may be significant"; this would be affected by the lack of it in the same manner as the Spanish translation.

Comma errors affecting meaning are frequent in both Spanish and English. In my opinion, the two errors pointed out show how a KIID's translator must be well equipped with linguistic skills, relating to the source as well as the target language (apart from, naturally, attention to detail). The fact that professional translators rely more on linguistic aspects (including grammar, context and punctuation) than subject-matter experts, and tend to pay special attention to these aspects, makes it likely that the translations concerned were carried out by subject-matter experts (although they might have been carried out by (un)professional translators).⁷

To close this section, I will refer to the specific lexical requirements for the KIID. The pursued scarcity of abbreviations and foreign terms (in contrast with other financial genres) has been confirmed in the corpus, in addition to attempts to avoid technical terms; these attempts are reflected, for example,

in the fact that certain risk factors are explained without the terms designating them being given.

7. Conclusions

The Key Investor Information document is a financial genre where marketing language, legalese and technical terms are avoided in order to describe an investment product—specifically, a UCITS fund—in a manner as impartial and simple as possible, for retail investors to be able to make an informed investment decision.

If the investment product is to be marketed in another country, the KIID must be translated into this country's official language or into a language approved by this country's authorities. Although the translation does not need to be sworn, civil liability can be incurred for the translated version's being misleading, inaccurate or inconsistent with the product's "prospectus". Given the rapidly increasing volume of UCITS funds, as well as the regulators' plans of extending the requirement of a KIID to other types of investment products, the KIID's already felt impact on the translation industry can be expected to grow (hand in hand with its impact on society).

This article has drawn attention to the genre and demonstrated the challenge it represents for both the translator and Translation Studies. From the translator, it requires sound knowledge of the subject-matter (investment funds) and of the UCITS regulations, as well as meticulous work, in order to

ensure that the investors do not miss any relevant information and that the information provided is presented in a concise, simple, clear and comparable manner, without overlooking any of the legal requirements. In this regard, the translator's mediating role is fundamental.

As far as Translation Studies is concerned, the KIID shows the considerable gap between research and practice in the area of financial translation (despite the significant efforts made recently, such as Alcalde 2014 and the COMENEGO project by Gallego-Hernández)⁸. As demonstrated in my article, the KIID does not share many of the characteristics of other financial genres, such as metaphors, abbreviations and the profusion of foreign terms, and deserves a place in the categorizations of economic (or financial) texts. Further efforts to bridge the mentioned gap are necessary, and could, in my opinion, bring about remarkable results, as has been the case in the area of theatre translation (Serón-Ordóñez 2014).

Notes

¹ In all the examples, the underlining is mine.

² Incidentally, UCITS funds have reached 9 trillion euros in March 2015 (EFAMA 2015).

³ For a discussion about this false perception, see Samuelsson-Brown (2004, 155). Some of the attempts made recently within Translation Studies to empower the translator (in relation, specifically, to theatre translation) are summarized in Serón-Ordóñez (2014, 53 and 55-56).

⁴ I have enclosed the term ‘subject-matter expert’ in quotation marks to indicate awareness of the fact that specialized translators can be considered subject-matter experts. As is widely known, degrees of expertise vary, and a certain—often high—degree of it is necessary for the source text’s comprehension and translation. A translator who specializes in finance can, indeed, be expected to know this area better than an economist specializing in a different area within economics.

⁵ Based on my own experience, I believe that translation practice trains the translator’s memory over the years to retain the terminology selected for the job at hand and keep to it throughout this job.

⁶ I would like to draw attention to *no garantiza* [is not a guarantee of] as a translation for “is not a guide to”. A more accurate translation would have been *no es indicativa de*. The full English sentence has given rise to widely

varied translations, including “La rentabilidad histórica no es indicativa de la rentabilidad futura.” and also: “La rentabilidad histórica no constituye ninguna orientación sobre [is no guidance to] la rentabilidad futura.” Despite the fact that someone who is knowledgeable in finance will be aware that all of the Spanish translations refer to the same reality, the impression that they each leave on the layman investor’s mind can be quite different and influence his/her investment decision unduly. This evidences the importance of accuracy in this type of translation, and the particular suitability of professional translators for the job. They are not as likely to be influenced by their knowledge of the financial area as subject-matter experts, and are more likely to pay attention to linguistic nuances than the latter (see note 7 below).

⁷ The idea that professional translators rely more on linguistics is indebted to Isaac Barba Redondo, a subject-matter expert in another field, as well as a bilingual linguist; more particularly, to the discussions we have had on the subject and to his doctoral thesis *Problemas conceptuales en la traducción técnica: textos de automoción*, a draft of which I was kindly allowed to read. My last sentence in note 6 above has also benefited from these sources.

⁸ COMENEGO: Corpus Multilingüe de Economía y Negocios. Accessed July 31, 2015. <http://m.dti.ua.es/es/comenego/comenego-corpus-multilingue-de-economia-y-negocios.html>

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Key Investor Information

This document provides you with key investor information about this fund. It is not marketing material. The information is required by law to help you understand the nature and the risks of investing in this fund. You are advised to read it so you can make an informed decision about whether to invest.

123 Fund, a sub-fund of ABC Fund SICAV (ISIN: 4321)

This fund is managed by ABC Fund Managers Ltd, part of the XYZ group of companies

Objectives and Investment Policy

Joint description of the objectives and policy of the UCITS in plain language (it is suggested not to copy-out the prospectus)

Essential features of the product which a typical investor should know:

- main categories of eligible financial instruments that are the object of investment
- a statement that the investor may redeem units on demand, and how frequently units are dealt in
- whether the UCITS has a particular target in relation to any industrial, geographic or other market sectors or specific classes of assets
- whether discretionary choices regarding particular investments are allowed, and whether the fund refers to a benchmark and if so which one
- a statement of whether any income arising from the fund is distributed or reinvested

Other information if relevant, such as:

- what type of debt securities the UCITS invests in
- information regarding any pre-determined pay off and the factors expected to determine performance
- if choice of assets is guided by growth, value or high dividends
- how use of hedging / arbitrage / leverage techniques may determine the fund's performance
- that portfolio transaction costs will have a material impact on performance
- minimum recommended holding term

Risk and Reward Profile

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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Narrative explanation of the indicator and its main limitations:

- Historical data may not be a reliable indication for the future
- Risk category shown is not guaranteed and may shift over time
- The lowest category does not mean 'risk free'
- Why the fund is in its specific category
- Details of nature, timing and extent of any capital guarantee or protection

Narrative presentation of risks materially relevant to the fund which are not adequately captured by the indicator:

- Credit risk, where a significant level of investment is made in debt securities
- Liquidity risk, where a significant level of investment is made in financial instruments that are likely to have a low level of liquidity in some circumstances
- Counterparty risk, where a fund is backed by a guarantee from, or has material investment exposure through contracts with, a third party
- Operational risks including safekeeping of assets
- Impact of any techniques such as derivative contracts

Charges for this Fund

The charges you pay are used to pay the costs of running the fund, including the costs of marketing and distributing it. These charges reduce the potential growth of your investment.

One-off charges taken before or after you invest	
Entry charge	[]%
Exit charge	[]%
This is the maximum that might be taken out of your money [before it is invested][before the proceeds of your investment are paid out].	
Charges taken from the fund over a year	
Ongoing charges	[]%
Charges taken from the fund under certain specific conditions	
Performance fee	[]% a year of any returns the fund achieves above the benchmark for these fees, [insert name of benchmark].

The **entry** and **exit charges** shown are maximum figures. In some cases you might pay less - you can find this out from your financial adviser.

The **ongoing charges** figure is based on expenses for the year ending []. This figure may vary from year to year. It excludes:

- Performance fees
- Portfolio transaction costs, except in the case of an entry/exit charge paid by the UCITS when buying or selling units in another collective investment undertaking

For more information about charges, please [see pages x to x / section x] of the fund's prospectus, which is available at www.ucitsfund/prospectus

Past Performance

The chart will be supplemented with prominent statements which:

- warn about its limited value as a guide to future performance
- indicate briefly which charges have been included or excluded
- state the year when the fund started to issue units
- indicate the currency in which past performance has been calculated.

Practical Information

- Name of the depositary
- Where and how to obtain further information about the UCITS (prospectus, reports & accounts)
- Where and how to obtain other practical information (e.g. where to find latest unit prices)
- A statement that tax legislation of the fund's Home State may have an impact on the personal tax position of the investor
- A statement that "[Name of management company] may be held liable solely on the basis of any statement contained in this document that is misleading, inaccurate or inconsistent with the relevant parts of the prospectus for the fund"
- Specific information relating to umbrella funds (e.g. any switching rights between sub-funds)
- Information about other share classes, if applicable (KII may be based on a representative class)

This fund is authorised in [name of Member State] and regulated by [identity of competent authority].

[Name of management company] is authorised in [name of Member state] on and regulated by [identity of competent authority].]

This key investor information is accurate as at [the date of publication].